

**Outcomes Report:
Belmont Forum e-Infrastructures & Data Management Project
(NSF Award #1650924)**

In 2015, an international partnership of science funding agencies known as the Belmont Forum (www.belmontforum.org) adopted an Open Data Policy and Principles (<http://www.belmontforum.org/about/open-data-policy-and-principles/>). The Policy and Principles advocate for rigorous, full-lifecycle research data management, data sharing, and open science, foreshadowing the [FAIR Data Principles](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) published by Force-11 in 2016. The adoption and implementation of the Policy and Principles signaled a commitment by global environmental change research funders to increase public access to scientific data, a step widely recognized as essential to making informed decisions in the face of rapid changes affecting the Earth's environment.

As a further sign of this commitment, five Belmont Forum partners funded a Collaborative Research Action (CRA) in 2016 to help make operational the Policy and Principles in its research program. The resulting "e-Infrastructures and Data Management (e-I&DM) Project" included members from the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF), UK Natural Environmental Research Council (NERC), France's Agence Nationale de Recherche (ANR), Taiwan's Ministry of Science and Technology (MoST), and the Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST).

Together, this multinational, interdisciplinary team coordinated outreach and collaborations with international data and environmental research groups to identify best practices for data management and developed numerous resources for the Belmont Forum for capacity building, researcher and agency training, proposal development/evaluation, research data publication, and programmatic evaluation metrics. Key deliverables of these efforts included:

- Data and Digital Outcomes Management Plan (DDOMP) template that member agencies may use as the basis for a Data Management Requirements Annex to CRA funding calls;
- Data Management Plan (DMP) Scorecard for proposal reviewers, Belmont Forum Secretariat, or others to quantitatively evaluate completeness of DMPs submitted with proposals relative to DDOMP criteria;
- Data Accessibility Statement (DAS) template that specifies how to access data underlying the research being published, intended for research teams to use when publishing research funded by Belmont Forum in scholarly journals;
- Data Management Skills Curricula Framework that outlines basic curricula/topics/skills to ensure a minimum level of knowledge required to conduct data-enabled science;
- [Online Data Management Toolkit](#) as a resource for Belmont Forum and others to find basic training materials and resources;
- Data Management Training Module for introductory training of Belmont funders, researcher-proposers, Group of Program Coordinators, Theme Program Officers, etc. on data management issues;

- Transdisciplinary Research and Data Management slide presentation co-developed with START, FutureEarth, and International Science Council;
- Evaluation Metrics White Paper outlining metrics to measure progress towards implementation of the Open Data Policy and Principles;
- Data Policy Comparison Tool that enables users to compare up to 3 member agency data policies simultaneously when considering CRA funding requirements;
- Presentations, posters, and papers by the project team given at international and domestic conferences to communicate to the research community and the broader public on efforts and outcomes of the e-I&DM project.

To ensure that these resources and deliverables continue to have beneficial impacts after NSF funding ends, the e-I&DM Coordination Office worked closely with the Belmont Forum Secretariat to integrate these resources into CRA programmatic processes on the Belmont Forum grant operations website, from scoping, call development, proposal submission and evaluation, to award, mid-term and end-term valorization, and publication of research. A key outcome of this effort is the initial acculturation of open data practices and values into the Belmont Forum's collaborative research funding program.

Another key e-I&DM activity, led by ANR, MoST, and JST, was to develop and manage a separate Belmont Forum funding call to identify best practices and innovative science-driven e-infrastructure to enable international research data sharing. The outcome of this effort is the [Science-driven e-Infrastructure Innovation for Enhancement of Transnational, Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Data User in Environmental Change](#) (SEI CRA), announced in 2017 with funding support from five member agencies; three projects were awarded in 2018 under this call.

Project coordination, communication and collaboration, led by NSF's awardee Arizona Geological Survey, involved international data and research groups, interest/working groups, and individuals affiliated with including, but not limited to:

- American Association for the Advancement of Science Research Fellows
- American Geophysical Union
- Citizen Science Organization
- CODATA
- DataONE
- EarthCube
- Earth Science Information Partners
- European Commission
- European Geophysical Union
- European Open Science Cloud
- European Space Agency
- FutureEarth
- GoFAIR
- Group on Earth Observations

- International Science Council-World Data System
- Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association
- Open Research Funders Group
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
- Research Data Alliance
- Society of Scholarly Publishing
- START International
- U.N. Convention to Combat Desertification
- U.N. Division of Sustainable Development Goals
- U.N. Statistics Commission
- U.S. Global Change Research Program
- World Meteorological Organization

The key outcome and most important legacy of this extensive coordination effort is the widespread international recognition of the Belmont Forum as a leader in Open Data policy, practices and resources for international, transdisciplinary global change research.